

The Real Life Benefits of Games

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Abstract

Games are degraded by some as having no world impact. Some naysayers say games are a waste of time and resources. However that simply is not true. In this paper I will demonstrate a real world example of games having a real world impact.

1 Introduction

Games. Games are a controversial topic. Gamers are often degraded as second class citizens. There has seemingly been a prejudice against games for thousands of years. Only some games are considered noble, while some are characterized as the scum of basement dwellers.

However things are changing. A new generation of gamers is changing the world for the greater. No longer will games be left to rot. The community will rise again and create a functioning society from the ashes.

This paper details a specific event that did just that, where two games players came together to add value to the immediate world.

2 The Deal of a Millennia

2.1 Midnight on a Monday

Just after the stoke of midnight on Monday October 18th, the local gaming community colloquially named "This shits bigger than March madness!" (an objectively true statement, as this shit really is, bigger than march madness) was playing their nightly gaming rounds in peace. The daily suite of games such as mancala, mini golf, archery among many others had been played and enjoyed by all.

Towards the end of a game of minigolf between clutch2dope and Zachrel, a game-altering statement (see: *Figure 1*) was issued by clutch:

"If Zachrel can get that in ≥ 2 I'll buy him a sub and such at phillyO's tomorrow"

This statement was unfortunately invalidated and short lived as clutch was unaware Zachrel had already provided his game-moves and clutch had won the game. However, this inspired an entire new challenge.

Figure 1: A game-altering statement.

2.2 A new challenge approaches.

Immediately after the conclusion of this game, clutch proposed a full gaming bet. The winner of the next game between Zachrel and clutch2dope would win a submarine sandwich and a drink from

Philadelphia Originals. After a short back and forth over the choice of game (see: Figure 2) the choice of Archery as the competition sport was made.

Figure 2: A short back and forth.

2.3 A troll from under the bridge.

Unfortunately for the participants of the game, immediately after the game message was sent declaring Archery as the set sport and initiating a GamePigeon game, an outside interloper decided to cause havoc. Christian Hartman (after a long period of inactivity) decided to interrupt the game and act as the other participant in the game sent by clutch. This additionally caused Zachrel to enter into this game and added to the confusion felt by all in the chat. Both clutch and Zachrel ended up scoring a full 30 points in each of their rounds. These scores were unfortunately invalid, Christian Hartman was removed from the chat and an entire new game was sent.

2.4 Games Games Games

A long battle subsequently began after the interloper was removed from the chat. Each participant gave it their all in order to win the coveted prize of a Philadelphia Originals submarine sandwich. The difficult game of Archery was a long fought battle that resulted in a campaign of determination. clutch nor Zachrel backed down to the challenge. The final scoring of the game came with the following outcome.

Player	Round 1	Round 2	Round 3
clutch (2dope)	30	29	n/a
Zachrelli	29	27	n/a

Table 1: Caption

2.5 To the victor goes the spoils!

After the conclusion of the game and Zachrel’s subsequent defeat clutch2dope had won the grand prize. The prize is listed below:

- (1) Philadelphia Originals Submarine Sandwich
- (1) drink from Philadelphia Originals

The participants then subsequently decided to schedule their post-game meetup. Zachrel expressed a schedule conflict which prohibited him from participating in this post-game ritual until after 1:30. clutch agreed on the timing and the date was set.

3 Conclusion

Games are more than just games. Games are people. Games are bonds. Games are family. Games are what make the world go round. Games are like a hot coffee on a cold day. Games are like a new pair of leather shoes with an automatic mechanism that adheres them to your feet. Games are like the Eiffel tower. Games are like a fresh slice of Swiss cheese on a porcelain plate. Games are like an

Oldsmobile that starts up for the first time. Games are like a honeysuckle that's just the right amount of rotted. Games are like standing up from a chair you've just sat in for 2 hours. Games are like a cup of tea brewed from the fresh dew of Bermuda grass. Games are like a car that doesn't shock you after you hot-wired it. Games are like . . .